

1 **Homeobox activation is an essential component of transformation.**

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6 Transformation proceeds following loss of tumor suppressor function or activation of oncogene, like
7 oncogenic transcription factors of the ETS family or oncogenic kinase mutants of the Ras pathway. We
8 studied whole transcription in human cells following Ras oncogene expression. We discovered strong
9 transcriptional activation of a network of homeobox transcription factors resulting from oncogene
10 expression *in vitro*. Activation of homeoboxes was quantitatively and qualitatively different when
11 comparing cells expressing wild-type or oncogenic mutant KRas. Expression of dominant negative p53
12 R175H, a tumor suppressor mutant that drives transformation in humans, was sufficient to induce
13 activation of the TGIF1 homeobox transcription factor. In vivo, we found homeobox activation in a murine
14 adipose stem cell model of tumorigenicity resulting from p53 inactivation. Tumorigenicity resulting from
15 p53-deficiency was associated with Hoxc and Hoxd family transcription factor induction. Consistent with a
16 functional relationship between homeobox activation resulting from tumor suppressor deficiency or
17 oncogene expression, expression of oncogenic RasG12V but not wild-type Ras resulted in Hoxc family
18 activation *in vitro*. Oncogenic but not wild-type Ras controlled expression of PAX8. Depletion of PAX8 in
19 transformed human cells was sufficient to abrogate induction of the major solid tumor gene ECT2,
20 demonstrating homeobox transcription factors maintain a transformed state. The data demonstrates
21 homeobox transcription factor transcriptional activation is an essential process in transformation.
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Results

We utilized an *in vitro* model of KRas driven transformation to study transcriptional dynamics of Ras oncogene transformation in human cells. For this system, we measured total transcription in AALE lung epithelial cells following expression of wild-type KRas or oncogenic KRas G12V.

We observed high magnitude activation of homeobox transcription factors following expression of KRas G12V.

KRAS G12V expression results in widespread homeobox activation.

Figure 1: Homeobox expression changes associated with expression of wild-type KRas.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3845	1.25E-104	0.1194	-21.7226819	-2.5931907	17252.28	KRAS	12/	
3217	7.51E-48	0.266	14.53275	3.8651382	174.47	HOXB7	32/	
139324	1.85E-25	0.5438	10.4280576	5.6703861	77.12	HDX	117/	
3200	2.62E-21	0.5976	9.4767498	5.6636961	67.73	HOXA3	171/	
23314	1.51E-20	0.4195	9.2919863	3.8983973	81.24	SATB2	189/	
3207	2.46E-19	0.5286	8.9904903	4.7527983	51.73	HOXA11	204/	
6899	6.06E-19	0.2468	8.8909636	2.1940141	294.25	TBX1	212/	
8538	2.12E-07	0.1547	5.1884122	0.8027554	319.04	BARX2	1355/	
56917	4.28E-06	0.23	4.5971941	1.0571487	214.07	MEIS3	1856/	
1745	3.31E-06	0.2931	4.6503777	1.3632269	90.88	DLX1	1807/	
9839	3.04E-02	0.6557	-2.1644192	-1.4192343	14.31	ZEB2	7205/	
94234	5.55E-02	0.1622	-1.9152914	-0.3106985	475.27	FOXQ1	8197/19751	

Figure 2: Homeobox expression changes associated with expression of oncogenic KRas G12V.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3845	2.38E-20	0.146	-9.243869	-1.3481302	9849.27	KRAS	118/	
8538	3.61E-16	0.166	-8.150997	-1.3508852	816.37	BARX2	186/	
56917	2.16E-14	0.207	-7.640991	-1.5821855	654.75	MEIS3	226/	
1745	1.37E-10	0.227	-6.418885	-1.4592006	277	DLX1	379/	
9839	1.22E-09	0.498	-6.077984	-3.026388	40.23	ZEB2	437/	
5452	2.35E-09	0.263	-5.97183	-1.5676655	128.68	POU2F2	453/	
6935	8.50E-09	0.263	-5.758177	-1.5152805	187.13	ZEB1	501/	
3217	1.29E-07	0.187	-5.280555	-0.988677	552.9	HOXB7	624/	
13932	1.29E-04	0.329	3.827719	1.2580651	121.91	HDX	1269/	
3200	2.93E-04	0.269	-3.620971	-0.9729006	223.63	HOXA3	1440/	
23314	2.25E-04	0.228	-3.689601	-0.8394392	238.72	SATB2	1388/	
3207	7.54E-03	0.251	-2.672198	-0.671092	146.48	HOXA11	2535/	
6899	9.05E-09	0.229	-5.74765	-1.3186224	957.41	TBX1	506/	
94234	1.04E-11	0.175	-6.800567	-1.1868965	788.18	FOXQ1	316/19958	

We study transformation in mammalian tissues, driven both by oncogene expression and by tumor suppressor loss or mutation. We asked whether expression of a dominant negative p53 point mutation sufficient to induce cancer in mammals could activate homeobox transcription. We observed activation of the *TGIF1* homeobox by p53 mutant R175H in non-transformed human breast epithelial cells (Figure 3).

Expression of a dominant negative p53 mutant *R175H* is sufficient to activate the *TGIF1* homeobox.

Figure 3: Expression of p53 R175H in non-transformed epithelial cells of the breast results in activation and differential expression of the *TGIF1* homeobox transcription factor.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7050	2.36E-02	0.977	-2.263007	-2.2104668	229.88	TGIF1	468/	
1894	4.98E-01	0.603	-0.677654	-0.4088964	884.27	ECT2	3257/14219	

After establishing homeobox activation resulting from oncogenic mutant Kras and dominant negative human mutant p53 in human cells, we evaluated the presence of quantitatively significant homeobox activation *in vivo* associated with tumorigenicity in an adipose stem cell (ASC) model where orthotopic injection of wild-type ASC is not tumorigenic while orthotopic injection of a p53 ASC counterpart is (Figure 4).

Tumorigenicity *in vivo* is associated with *HOXC/D* activation.

Figure 4: *HOXC* activation in adipose stem cells with engineered deletion of p53.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_51_P385684	4.79E-11	-5.99E+01	16.285478	-3.9370235	Hoxc12	113/	
A_52_P283656	3.79E-05	-8.87	1.811916	-1.12668519	Hoxc5	8310/38913	

Figure 5: *HOXD* activation in adipose stem cells with engineered deletion of p53.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_52_P407049	1.56E-11	-7.00E+01	17.260165	-5.24010227	Hoxd10	56/	
A_51_P112319	7.02E-11	-5.69E+01	15.938506	-5.22690885	Hoxd11	143/	
A_52_P591310	9.91E-10	-3.94E+01	13.358752	-3.05809761	Hoxd13	491/	
A_51_P269053	5.45E-09	-3.11E+01	11.582795	-2.29762421	Hoxd3os1	922/38913	

Since deletion of p53 resulted in *HOXC/D* activation in adipose stem cells (ASC), and since transplantation of p53 *-/-* ASC but not wild-type results in tumorigenicity *in vivo*, we were able to conclude that *HOXC* and *HOXD* activation resulting from p53 deficiency is associated with tumorigenicity *in vivo*.

HOX family transcription factors serve important functions in human development. Since we found that *HOXC/D* activation in mice was a signature transcriptional aspect of transformation and tumorigenicity resulting from transformation due to p53 loss, we asked whether mutant *KRas* oncogene expression was also associated with *HOXC/D* activation. Expression of the *HOXC* family was activated following expression of *KRas* G12V but not wild-type *KRas* (Figure 6 and 7). In addition, an antisense message from the *HOXD* family, *HAGLR*, was repressed by wild-type *KRas* but activated by *KRas* G12V.

Expression of oncogenic KRas G12V but not wild-type KRas results in HOXC/D activation.

Figure 6: HOXC/D expression changes associated with expression of wild-type KRas.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
100874366	2.01E-11	0.238	6.7051236	1.5958019	109.47	HOXC13-AS	619/	
3224	1.43E-07	0.2956	5.2618652	1.5551563	87.79	HOXC8	1295/	
100874363	1.05E-04	0.5144	3.8784668	1.9950396	20.78	HOXC-AS1	2791/	
3221	1.21E-04	0.4762	3.8431161	1.8300211	23.7	HOXC4	2841/	
3225	1.27E-04	0.2199	3.8327992	0.8428472	148.4	HOXC9	2856/	
3227	4.45E-03	0.2979	2.8444549	0.8472591	55.51	HOXC11	5007/	
3222	3.32E-01	0.4915	0.9703514	0.4769204	18.05	HOXC5	13036/	
401022	5.42E-08	0.9927	5.4369466	5.3974667	20.93	HAGLR	1176/	

Figure 7: HOXC/D expression changes associated with expression of oncogenic KRas G12V.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3225	1.05E-09	0.194	-6.101872	-1.1852946	351.71	HOXC9	431/	
3224	1.16E-06	0.213	-4.862503	-1.033462	225.59	HOXC8	741/	
3223	1.32E-04	0.27	-3.822623	-1.0337442	105.29	HOXC6	1277/	
3227	7.15E-04	0.257	-3.383835	-0.871285	113.98	HOXC11	1619/	
100874366	4.83E-03	0.204	-2.817918	-0.576056	232.03	HOXC13-AS	2317/	
3222	12.29E-02	0.412	-2.275482	-0.9368194	34.73	HOXC5	3368/	
3221	5.08E-01	0.362	-0.662073	-0.2394585	45.53	HOXC4	12825/	
401022	3.99E-10	0.319	-6.254466	-1.9937107	116.77	HAGLR	404/	

Expression of oncogenic KRas G12V but not wild-type KRas results in PAX8 activation.

Figure 8: PAX8 expression changes associated with expression of wild-type KRas.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7849	3.84E-18	0.3631	8.6833105	3.1526158	64.56	PAX8	242/	
654433	1.42E-82	0.2409	19.2495166	4.6369663	301.31	PAX8-AS1	15/	

Figure 9: PAX8 expression changes associated with expression of oncogenic KRas G12V.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7849	2.59E-21	0.212	-9.478148	-2.0070351	330.78	PAX8	107/	
654433	4.31E-40	0.149	-13.253512	-1.9713442	1615.07	PAX8-AS1	32/	

Finally, we studied control of transformation by PAX8 by measuring total transcription following PAX8 depletion in human cells, to understand its relevance in transformation and/or maintenance of the transformed state as a homeobox.

1 **PAX8 depletion is sufficient to collapse the transformed state, indicating PAX8 executes**
2 **maintenance of transformation.**

3 Figure 10: PAX8 depletion results in silencing of ECT2, demonstrating control of transformation.

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7849	4.14E-08	0.469	5.4846307	2.5728186	6490.02	PAX8	235/	
1894	1.15E-04	0.291	3.8567267	1.1205178	2917.18	ECT2	832/17131	

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7 **Discussion**

8 We demonstrated here that homeobox activation is an essential component of transformation,
9 evidenced by a simultaneous induction of a quantitatively important multitude of factors with homeotic
10 potential, by oncogenic mutant KRas but not wild-type KRas following expression in human cells. Despite
11 the contributions of a multitude of factors to the transformed state, PAX8 is sufficient to maintain it and
12 likely functions in a hierarchical manner as a master-type homeobox during transformation. The function
13 of a PAX8-AS1 antisense transcript is poorly understood but likely biologically relevant.
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Methods

We utilized the microarray and/or RNA-sequencing datasets (GSE146479, GSE162341, GSE43804 and GSE83100) to study homeobox transcription in human cells and in vivo during transformation in conjunction with R-based computational methods.